

Dipole Moments and I.R. Spectral Studies of the Complexes formed in the Mixtures of Phenylenediamine with Naphthols

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Dipole moments and I.R. spectral measurements of the complexes formed in the mixtures of *o*-phenylenediamine + α -naphthol, + β -naphthol, and *m*-phenylenediamine + α -naphthol have been made. The nature of complexes formed in these mixtures have been discussed.

SOLID+liquid phase diagrams indicated¹ the presence of 1/1 and 1/2 complexes in the mixtures of *o*-phenylenediamine + α -naphthol (1/1), *o*-phenylenediamine + β -naphthol (1/1), *m*-phenylenediamine + α -naphthol (1/1), *m*-phenylenediamine + β -naphthol (1/2), *p*-phenylenediamine + α -naphthol (1/2), and *p*-phenylenediamine + β -naphthol (1/2). In this paper we report the dipole moments of the 1/1 complexes formed in the first three mixtures and I.R. spectral measurements of all the complexes and the pure components. Dipole moment measurements may be related to hydrogen bonding², dipole association³, association constants⁴, interaction energy⁵ and to the nature of forces⁶ operating between the components of the mixtures. We restricted our measurements of dipole moment to 1/1 complexes as Weissberger method⁷ of calculating induced moments may be applied to systems forming 1/1 complexes.

Experimental

o-, *m*-, and *p*-Phenylenediamines were fractionally crystallized from ethyl alcohol. α -, and β -Naphthols were fractionally crystallized from benzene. The purities of the samples were checked by thin layer chromatography and by determining the melting temperatures, which agreed to within ± 0.1 K with the values reported in literature^{8,9}.

The complexes were prepared in molar ratios calculated from phase diagrams¹ by the method described earlier¹⁰. The dielectric constants of the complexes in benzene determined from the capacity measurements using Universal Impedance Bridge (type EE 01-02a, Toshniwal) at 308.15 K. The samples were placed in a cell containing a coaxial brass cylinder, the mouth of the cell was closed with a glass stopper to eliminate errors due to evaporation. The cell containing the sample was placed in a thermostat whose temperature was controlled to 0.1 K. The instrument was calibrated beforehand with several samples of pure liquids such as benzene, toluene, cyclohexane, chlorobenzene, carbon tetra-

chloride, *o*-xylene, and *m*-xylene. The values of dielectric constant for these compounds agreed to within 0.001 with the corresponding literature values^{8,11}. The refractive indices were measured using an Abbe refractometer which was thermostated at 308.15 K by circulating water through it.

Specific volumes were measured from their density values. The densities were measured using a pycnometer designed for this purpose at 308.15 K in a thermostat. I.R. spectral measurements of the pure components and the complexes were made in chloroform with Specord 71-IR. I.R. spectra of pure components were taken at different dilutions.

Results

The dipole moments were calculated by the method of Richard and Walker¹². The details are shown in Table 1.

The dissociation of the complexes in solution was studied from optical measurements by various methods¹³⁻¹⁵. Optical measurements were made in alcohol using filters of 546 and 436 nm (Erma Colorimeter) by the method described earlier¹⁶. The nature of the complexes in solution phase was found to be the same as in the solid phase. Plots of optical density against concentration were linear indicating that dissociation is very small and does not have any significant effect on dipole moment.

Discussion

The dipole moments in Table 1 have been collected (i) to determine the angle between the donor and acceptor molecules in the complex, and (ii) to study dipole interactions. As is evident from Table 1, μ_{complex} is greater than the sum of dipole moments of its components and so it is not feasible to determine the angle between the two interacting molecules. The main stumbling block seems to be the changes in the dipole moments of donor and acceptor molecules when they interact to form the complex. This interaction causes a

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TABLE 1—DIPOLE MOMENTS OF PURE COMPONENTS AND COMPLEXES

Substance	α	β	γ	μ/D	$\Delta\mu/D$	Induced moment/D
<i>o</i> -phenylenediamine				1.46		
<i>m</i> -phenylenediamine				1.80		
α -naphthol				1.46		
β -naphthol				1.56		
<i>xo</i> -phenylenediamine + (1 - <i>x</i>) α -naphthol	9.735	0.932	-0.489	3.531	0.61	0.2
<i>xo</i> -phenylenediamine + (1 - <i>x</i>) β -naphthol	11.464	0.933	-0.165	3.76	0.75	0.2
<i>xm</i> -phenylenediamine + (1 - <i>x</i>) α -naphthol	8.663	0.187	-0.379	3.32	0.06	0.2

polarization which changes dipole moments of the individual components by an unknown amount. Thus the change in dipole moment $\Delta\mu$, i.e., $\mu_{complex} - (\mu_1 + \mu_2) = \Delta\mu$, is either due to bond formation or due to induced dipole moments. The induced dipole moment in these complexes have been calculated by the method of Hampson and Weissberger⁷. The induced moments have been calculated by assuming the distance *r* to be 5 Å° which is quite reasonable¹⁷. The induced moments of the 1/1 complexes thus calculated have been compared with the corresponding $\Delta\mu$ values in Table 1.

In the complexes of *m*-phenylenediamine + α -naphthol (Table 1), the major contribution to the value of $\Delta\mu$ is from induced moments, indicating that dipole-dipole forces are more prominent in this complex. In the complexes of *o*-phenylenediamine + α -naphthol, and + β -naphthol, it is evident that $\Delta\mu$ is not solely caused by dipole-dipole interactions or induced moments. The higher values of $\Delta\mu$ indicates that there is an appreciable increase of moment on complex formation. A part of change is probably due to induced moments and remaining due to hydrogen bond formation.

TABLE 2—I. R. ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES OF THE PURE COMPONENTS AND COMPLEXES

Substance	Hydrogen bond cm ⁻¹	O-H bending cm ⁻¹	O-H out of plane deformation/cm ⁻¹
α -Naphthol	2930,3480	1350,1375	—
β -naphthol	3450	1370	—
<i>o</i> -phenylenediamine	2920,3300	—	700-850
<i>m</i> phenylenediamine	2920,3300	—	700-850
<i>p</i> -phenylenediamine	2920,3300	—	720-820
<i>xo</i> -phenylenediamine + (1 - <i>x</i>) α -naphthol	2940,3300	1350,1380	700-850
<i>xo</i> -phenylenediamine + (1 - <i>x</i>) β -naphthol	2940 3310,3480	1365,1380	700-820
<i>xm</i> -phenylenediamine + (1 - <i>x</i>) α -naphthol	2960,3100-3200,3320	1310,1360	710-830
<i>xm</i> -phenylenediamine + (1 - <i>x</i>) β -naphthol	2960,3100-3200,3320	1350,1370	710-840
<i>xp</i> -phenylenediamine + (1 - <i>x</i>) α -naphthol	2900	1385	—
<i>xp</i> -phenylenedia mine + (1 - <i>x</i>) β -naphthol	2920,3300	1370	700-800

I.R. absorption frequencies for the pure components and the complexes are recorded in Table 2. The infrared absorption frequencies indicate the presence of hydrogen bonding in the 1/1 complexes and also in the 1/2 complexes formed in the mixtures of *m*-phenylenediamine + β -naphthol, *p*-phenylenediamine + α -naphthol, and *p*-phenylenediamine + β -naphthol.

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